

ETHICAL IDEALS IN FORMING SPIRITUAL-MORAL QUALITIES OF FUTURE DOCTORS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the role of moral ideals in the formation of moral and ethical qualities of future doctors, professional ethics, and moral and educational events organized outside the auditorium.*

Keywords: *future doctor, spiritual and moral ideal, spiritual and moral qualities, spirituality, medical profession, professional ethics, moral ethics, professional duty.*

A person is not born with innate morality. The spiritual and moral qualities of a person represent the level of spiritual values he possesses. A person's goals and thoughts reflect his acquired knowledge and worldview. Spirituality helps to determine the life possibilities of a person. A person's heart is related to his mental activity. A person's historical, spiritual, national-social way of life is reflected in a person. Spiritual and moral qualities give meaning to the personal life of every person. Within the framework of his spiritual and professional world, a person asks himself questions and finds answers: Why am I living? What is my goal in becoming a doctor? What are compassion and cruelty? How is naturalness and fakeness manifested in a doctor? What is beauty? Ugly? such as.

The level of spirituality of a doctor is reflected in what moral standards he follows in the society where he lives, what values he has mastered and his contribution to society. Morality is one of the dimensions of human spirituality.

Spiritual and moral qualities are related to the psyche of a person and his ideals.

In the national encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, the term ideal is defined as follows: "Ideal (Greek idea - symbol, concept) - the highest example, perfection of something and event; a higher goal that some individual, group of individuals, class and society strive for. Socio-political ideal perfect social system; moral ideal, perfect human qualities, human relations; the aesthetic ideal is a beautiful appearance, character, description that has matured in every way" [1; p. 76].

Philosophy. In the short explanatory dictionary, the word ideal is described somewhat more widely: Ideal - (derived from French ideal, Latin idealus) is used in the meanings of image, criterion, perfection. Ideal is the highest goal of aspiration. In a broad sense, an ideal can be the best, most valuable, most perfect state of a thing or a phenomenon [2; p. 145].

On the basis of the philosophical and pedagogical interpretation of the ideal, the highest goals of a person and the need to strive for perfection are understood. In the ideal, the striving for perfection, personal qualities, actions and activities of each person are expressed. The highest goal of a person is manifested in the form of his desire to acquire the secrets of morality and sophistication, legal, political, and economic outlook. A person with a high goal believes in the correctness of the idea he has chosen, can assess its social and political significance. A

person's wishes are the basis for the formation of a goal of great socio-educational importance in them. Therefore, the desire to achieve the same high goals determines the spiritual and moral qualities of a person.

Moral ideals do not have an absolute description. They develop, improve as a model, determine the prospects of personal development. Development is characterized as humanistic moral ideals, therefore, they appear as a motive for personal improvement. Ideals are bound by historical period and generation, the best humanitarian traditions are acquired by inheritance and primarily through education.

Moral ideals appear as the highest criterion of a person's motivational-value-oriented attitude. It is characterized by the understanding of the duty and responsibility of the doctor to the society. The attitude of a person directs a person to the objective relationship of objects and events in the environment and other people, and evaluates the subjective position of a person relative to this or that subject, and at the same time evaluates its importance. In this sense, "attitude" appears simultaneously in two cases: as a procedural description (adds an act of evaluation) and stable personal education, which shows the person as a carrier of humanitarian values (value approach). In this case, the person appears as an activity provider in connection with the reality of existence, he has the opportunity to choose and directs the nature of his developing activity based on it. Relationships are carried out through the interaction of the environment and the person and determine the orientation of the person in terms of content, and connect the main phenomenon of subjectivity (views, motives, needs, evaluations, feelings, habits, value attitudes) and coordinates.

However, not only his subjectivity, but also the objectively given content is reflected in personal relations, because objective goals are presented in it. As an objective moment of personal relations, his social position emerges, and it shows the complexity of relations, which arise in the referent system of interpersonal relations and in socially significant activities. The content of a person's relationship can be the object and subject (values) of motives, and they are manifested in his mind in a specific social position [3].

Norms, demands, ideals, and cultural values set by society are accepted and assimilated by individuals individually and selectively. Therefore, the axiological attitude of the doctor does not always correspond to the values accepted and recognized by the society. When the society's values become an incentive and a motivating force for action, when they are consciously accepted and mastered by a person and when they correspond to his personal value, call, ideal, goal, they are appropriate only. ladi

Thus, issues of ethics and deontology are especially relevant in the training of medical personnel. The existence of formed moral qualities is of great importance for future doctors, because in their work, the owners of this profession are faced with the pain and difficult emotional experiences of patients and their relatives. Future doctors will need to be taught how to interact with patients, explain medical instructions, and encourage them to receive proper treatment.

Medicine is not only a specialty, but also a profession that requires special personal qualities. Consequently, the formation of the required spiritual and moral culture becomes the basis of educational activities in the training of future doctors.

In the course of its activity, the pedagogical team solves the issues of increasing the efficiency of training future doctors and forming their professional and ethical qualities. The

preparation of future doctors for their professional activities, of course, includes a deep understanding of their professional duty, professional and moral responsibility for the quality and result of their work. It is very important to develop moral qualities in future doctors, such as humanitarianism, compassion, kindness to others, and the desire to help everyone who needs help, and a medical worker should have a high sense of empathy.

In order to form the image of the future profession and important professional qualities among future doctors, it is necessary to build the educational process and extracurricular activities in accordance with this goal, to use all the educational potential of the educational institution to the maximum.

It is necessary to take into account the main tasks and place of science in the system of training a specialist in a certain medical profile, paying attention to the most important topics for the formation of moral and moral qualities of future doctors. Also, it is necessary to make maximum use of the educational potential of each subject in order to form the professional ideal of students.

In the educational process, professors and teachers, in addition to forming the spiritual and moral qualities of future doctors, contribute to the development of communication skills of students, their understanding of the essence and importance of the chosen specialty, its role in strengthening health in society, self-development take active actions and try to develop themselves.

Thus, in the formation of spiritual and moral qualities of future doctors, it is of great importance to hold trainings in addition to the audience, which instill in them love for patients and increase interest in their chosen profession. The holding of such events leaves a deep impression on the minds of future doctors and instills in them pride in the right choice, a responsible attitude to the occupation, being in demand in modern society, quickly adapting to society, z allows to successfully form a profession.

There are various non-auditory educational activities for the formation of moral and ethical qualities of future doctors: meetings with employers, specialists of medical institutions, scientific-practical conferences of students, competitions of professional skills, involvement of employers in qualifying exams, various creative competitions and Science Olympiads are among them.

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